

CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF *Coriolopsis brysina*

¹Ofodile L. N., ²Uma, N. U., ³Simmonds, M. S. J

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Yaba College of Technology, Yaba, Lagos, Nigeria, ²Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, Richmond TW9 3AB, UK, ³Department of Botany and Microbiology, University of Lagos, Akoka, Lagos, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The morphological and chemical characteristics of *Coriolopsis brysina* (L.) Pers. were determined and its crude n-hexane: diethyl ether, chloroform: acetone and methanol extracts were also screened for antimicrobial activity. Results showed that the fruitbody was sessile, pileate and reflexed-effused. The pileus was applanate, concentrically zonate, with round pores and cinnamon context and the hyphal system was trimitic with oblong, yellowish colored spores. The chemical spot tests revealed that the tissue darkened with potassium hydroxide, and reacted with ferric chloride to produce brown colour. It was dextrinoid and produced characteristic colours with ammonium hydroxide, ferrous sulphate and sulphuric acid. None of the solvent extracts were active against *Cladosporium herbarium*. The hexane: ether and chloroform: acetone extracts were active against *Pseudomonas syringae* and *Bacillus subtilis* whereas the methanol extract had no effect on the two bacteria. Preliminary chemical tests on the extracts of *C. brysina* suggest that the n-hexane: ether and chloroform: acetone extracts could contain phenolics and terpenoids.

KEYWORDS: *C. Brysina*, morphological and chemical characteristics, solvents, antimicrobial activity

INTRODUCTION

Coriolopsis is a mushroom genus in the family polyporaceae (Ryvarden and Johanson, 1980; Ofodile, 2006) in the order Aphyllophorales with corky, woody, leathery, papery basidiocarps known as polypores (Zjawiony, 2004). Aphyllophorales are mushrooms in the class basidiomycetes with holobasidia but usually lack gills (Kirk *et al.*, 2001).

Western Scientists started to investigate the mechanisms of health effects of mushrooms at the end of the 1960s (Irfans and Atiya, 1998). According to a recent biological evaluation of over 200 fungal species, more than 75% of screened polypores showed strong antimicrobial activity (Suay *et al.*, 2000). Some polypores from Nigeria have also been screened for antimicrobial activity and were found to inhibit the growth of two plant pathogens (*Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas syringae*) but had no effect on *Cladosporium herbarum* (Ofodile, 2004; Ofodile, 2005; Ofodile *et al.*, 2005a). Two triterpenoids known as colossolactone E and 23-hydroxycolossolactone E purified from *Ganoderma colossum* (Fr.) C. F. Baker collected from Yaba, Lagos were also active against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas syringae* which were tested using thin layer chromatographic agar overlay method (Ofodile *et al.*, 2005b)

Many characterizations of fungi have been based on comparison of macroscopic and microscopic structures of the fungi with that found in the literatures (Zoberi, 1972; Rammeloo and Walley, 1993) and several chemical tests are also traditionally employed as criteria in the characterization of mushrooms (Zoberi, 1972; De Rosa, 2003). The darkening of the colour of the basidiocarp on application of Potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution is recognised as due to a xanthochroic reaction. This has been claimed by taxonomist to be a characteristic of the fungi that produce basidiocarps with brown context and trama belonging to the hymenochataceae only (Pamasto and Pamasto, 1979; Roy and Dutta, 1990).

There are scanty reports on the antimicrobial activity of polypores from Nigeria and they are also hardly used in therapeutic medicine mainly for lack of enough documentation of their identities. This work provides information on the relevant characteristics used in the identification of *Coriolopsis brysina* and the effects of the hexane: ether, chloroform: acetone and methanol extracts of the mushroom on some plant pathogens. The extracts were also screened for the presence of phenolics and terpenes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection and preservation of mushroom specimens

The samples were collected in the mornings to ensure that they were fresh. A pocketknife was used to scrape the mushroom from wood. The length and diameters of the specimens were measured with a ruler. The details of the macroscopic features, colour, smell and texture of the specimens were recorded according to the methods of Ryvarden and Johanson (1980) and Laessle (1998). The basidiocarps *Coriolopsis brysina* (L.) Pers. were from the dead log of *Treculia africana*, Obosi, Anambra State, Nigeria. Fifty specimens of the mushroom were observed in the field and collected in August 2003. The Voucher specimens were deposited in the Herbarium of RBG, Kew, UK.

Preparation of spore prints

Mature basidiocarps of the specimens were used for the spore prints. The spore prints of the polypore were made by placing a strip of black paper beneath the specimen with the pores in the vertical position to ensure the release of spores. Specimens were collected in dry weather so they were wrapped in wet newspaper overnight to moisten them before making the prints. Spore prints were collected after about 12 hours and stored in the refrigerator (Zoberi, 1973; Ryvarden and Johansen, 1980).

Characterization of mushroom specimens

Morphological and chemical characteristics of the specimens were obtained according to (Zoberi, 1973; Ryvarden and Johansen, 1980; De Rosa, 2003). Many determinations of fungal identification have been based upon comparison of the macroscopic and microscopic structures of the fungi with that found in the literature (Zoberi, 1972; Rammeloo and Walley, 1992; Smith and Sivasithamparam, 2003). Therefore, the morphological characteristics of the fungi observed in this study were also compared with those of Fidalgo (1968); Geber and Loguercio-Leite (2000); Ryvarden and Johansen, (1980). The specimens collected in Nigeria were also compared with herbarium specimens at the Royal Botanic Garden (RBG), Kew.

Morphological examination of mushroom specimens

Macroscopic examination

The fruiting season, shape, width, length, thickness, texture, and smell of the fruit bodies, colour, texture, shape, surface margin, area of attachment, and behaviour on touch of the pileus were assessed. The texture, colour and diameter of the context, colour changes, diameters of the pore surfaces were determined using the methods of Ryvarden and Johansen, (1980).

Microscopic examination

Tissues, and spores were observed under a binocular microscope (Leica DMLB) at $\times 63$ magnification (2mm equivalent to $1\mu\text{m}$). Photomicrographs of tissues and spores were taken with a digital camera (AF micro-Nikon, 60mm f/2.8D), which was connected to a computer (Dell Latitude, Pentium 111).

Slides of the specimens were prepared using drops of KOH solution on a clean, grease-free slide. Minute pieces of tissue were removed from the pileus surface, the cortex, and tubes of the basidiocarp with the aid of a forceps, placed in the mounting solution and covered with a clean slip. The cover slip was gently tapped to spread out the tissue, so that the structures could be easily observed. Spores were scraped from the pore surface into the mounting solution for observation. Slides were also prepared with ammonium hydroxide as the mounting solution. Types of hyphal system, number, colour, diameter, presence or absence of cystidia were assessed. Hyphal diameters (20 each) were measured with caution avoiding collapsed hyphae. The diameters, shape of spores were also measured as above. Caution was taken to avoid very young and immature spores. The averages of the sizes obtained were regarded as the diameter of the hyphae and spores.

Chemical spot test on mushroom specimens

The chemical tests employed were methods of De Rosa (2003); and Zoberi (1972)

Ferric chloride (FeCl_3) test:

Five drops of 5% solution of ferric chloride in water were applied to a mass of tissues (20mg) of the sample and allowed to stand under observation. The reaction was recorded.

Melzer's reagent test:

Chloral hydrate (20 grams) was mixed with iodine (0.5 gram), potassium iodide (1.5 gram) and water (20 millilitres). The mixture was warmed with stirring to dissolve. Five drops were mixed with a mass of tissues (20mg) of the sample and was allowed to stand for 10-20 minutes and reactions was recorded.

10% Ammonium Hydroxide (NH₄OH) test:

Ammonium hydroxide (10%) was mixed in enough water to make 100 milliliters of solution. Five drops were then applied to a mass of tissues (10mg) of the sample and were allowed to stand for 10-20 minutes and reaction was recorded.

Sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) test:

Two drops of concentrated sulphuric acid (18 molar) were applied to a mass of tissues (20mg) of the sample and was allowed to stand for 10-20 minutes and reaction was recorded.

Ferrous sulphate (Fe₂SO₄) test:

Five drops of 5% ferrous sulphate solution was applied to a mass of tissues (20mg) of the sample and was allowed to stand for 10-20 minutes and reaction was recorded.

Antimicrobial activity

Strains of bacteria and fungi

Assays were performed against two bacteria, *Bacillus subtilis* IMI347329 and *Pseudomonas syringae* IMI34748, which were grown on the nutrient agar (Oxoid CM3) at 37°C for 24h and stored at 4°C. The fungus *Cladosporium herbarum* IMI 300461 was grown on Malt extract (Oxoid L39, 2%) agar (1.5%) medium at 25°C. The sporulating cultures were kept at 4°C.

Preparation of mushroom specimens

Ground mushroom samples were sequentially extracted with three combinations of solvents to ensure selective extraction of compounds based on their polarity. Samples (1.5g) of the species were first extracted with n-hexane: diethyl ether (1:1) overnight at room temperature. The n-hexane: diethyl ether extract was filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper and was air-dried. The residue was further extracted overnight with chloroform: acetone (1:1), then with 80% aqueous methanol to provide chloroform; acetone and 80% methanol extracts. They were filtered into weighed vials using Whatman filter paper. The weight of each extract was determined and the final residue discarded.

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) bioassay

The TLC agar overlay method (Rahalison *et al.*, 1991) was used to test the activity of the mushroom extracts. The hexane: diethyl ether extracts were reconstituted in chloroform, while the chloroform: acetone and methanol extracts were reconstituted in acetone and methanol respectively.

Antibacterial assay

Aliquots (100µg) of each extract were spotted on the precoated TLC plates (1.05554 aluminum sheets, 20 by 20cm, silica gel 60 F₂₅₄, Merck). The chromatograms were eluted with the following mobile phases (i) the n-hexane/diethyl ether extract with 100% chloroform (ii) the chloroform: acetone extract with chloroform: acetone (9:1) and (iii) the 80% methanol extract with chloroform: acetone: water (75:25:2). Aliquot (1µl) of a chloramphenicol solution (1mg ml⁻¹) was used as a positive control. Nutrient agar (2.8g ml⁻¹) seeded with test organism adjusted to $\times 10^7$ was evenly spread on the air dried TLC chromatograms fixed in assay trays (22×22cm) and excess medium quickly poured out of the trays. TLC plates without control or antimicrobial agent were used as negative controls. Plates were incubated overnight at 37°C after which a p-iodonitrotetrazolium violet solution (0.05mg ml⁻¹ in 5% aqueous EtOH) was spread evenly on the plates and incubated further for 1hour at 37°C. Growth inhibition zones were observed as clear spots against pink background.

Antifungal assay

The antifungal activity (Homans and Fuchs, 1970) was carried out on the two species of polypore by spraying the conidia of *Cladosporium herbarium* suspension in a malt extract (2%) solution. Aliquots (100µg) of each sample were spotted on the precoated TLC plates (1.05554 aluminum sheets, 20 by 20cm, silica gel 60 F₂₅₄, Merck) and eluted as above. Nystatin (1µg) was used as a positive control while the TLC plates without extract

or antifungal agents were regarded as the negative control. The seeded plates were incubated in moist, sealed container for 72hours at 25°C. Growth inhibition zones were observed as above.

Chemical analysis

The reconstituted n-hexane: diethyl ether, chloroform: acetone and methanol extracts of the mushroom species were spotted on silica gel TLC plate (20×20cm) and developed with solvents as above. To screen the extracts for terpenoids and phenolics the chromatograms were sprayed with anisaldehyde-sulphuric acid solution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphological characterization

Coriolopsis byrsina (Accession number K (M) 121125): The fruit body was annual, sessile, pileate, reflexed-effused with numerous small pileus, which was thin and flexible 1-3mm thick, 1-8cm x 1-3cm in diameter with decurrent pore layer. Pileus was applanate, narrowly concentrically zonate, golden upper surface with concentric zone of greenish-brown which turns entirely rusty brown when dry and velutinate soft to touch, margin thin and wavy, covered with green algae in some specimens (Plate 1A-A₁). Pores surface cinnamon, pores round and entire, 5-6 per mm tubes concolorous with pore surface (Plate 1A₁). Context was also cinnamon, 1-2 mm thick. (Plate1A). Hyphal system was trimitic. The binding hyphae are hyaline to pale golden brown, solid, moderately branched; some were twisted richly. The system was dominated by the skeletal hyphae that were thick walled, yellow to golden brown, 3-6.5 μm (Plate 2a).

Plate 1: Photographs of the basidiocarp A; pileus surface and A₁; pore surface of *Coriolopsis byrsina*, Plate 2: Photomicrographs of the hyphal system a; skeletal hyphae, b; generative hypha and c; basidiospores.

Generative hyphae thin-walled and with clamps, 1-3 μm wide (Plate 2b). Spores were oblong, 4.5 x 2.5-3.2 μm , thin walled hyaline to very yellowish (Plate 2c) and the spore print was black.

Chemical characteristics of the polypores

The results of the chemical characterization of the mushroom specimens are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Reaction the tissues of *Corioloopsis brysina* with various reagents

Reagent	Reaction
FeCl ₃	Colour changed to brown immediately
Melzer's reagent	Colour changed to reddish brown
KOH	Colour changed to black
NH ₄ OH	Colour changed to deep brown
FeSO ₄	Colour changed to brown
H ₂ SO ₄	Colour changed to blood red

The characteristics of *C. brysina* corresponded with those documented by Ryvarden and Johanson, (1980) and Laessoe, (1998), except that the sizes of the spores of the specimens described by them were larger in diameter (3-8.5 μm). The colour change of the tissues in to brown with ferric chloride is an indication that it could contain phenolic compounds. It also showed xanthochroic reactions because the tissues turned black with potassium hydroxide. The polypore was dextrinoid and also produced characteristic colours with ammonium hydroxide, ferrous sulphate and sulphuric acid, and when sprayed with anisaldehyde-sulphuric acid solution produced blue to violet spots on the TLC plates, which could be used for its identification. According to Zoberi (1972); and De Rosa (2003) tissues of species of macro fungi produce characteristic colour in different chemical reagents that could be used to differentiate them.

The results of screening the three solvent extracts of *Corioloopsis brysina* against *Pseudomonas syringae*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Cladosporium herbarum* showed that none of the extracts were active against *C. herbarium*. The hexane: ether and chloroform: acetone extracts of *C. brysina* were active against *B. subtilis* and *P. syringae* whereas methanol extract was not active against the organisms. The activity of the different solvent extracts of the polypore against the two bacteria were similar and at the same zones on the TLC plates suggesting that the same compounds could be responsible for their activity against the two bacteria (Table 1).

Table 2: Antibacterial activity of extracts of *Corioloopsis brysina* (100 μg) on *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas syringae* sprayed on TLC plates

Extraction solvent Sample	Hex:Eth		Chl:Ace		Meth	
	Rf	Activity	Rf	Activity	Rf	Activity
<i>C. brysina</i>	0.00	+	0.00	+	ni	ni
	0.20	+	0.10	+	ni	ni

Hex:Eth; hexane:diethylether, Chl:Ace; chloroform:acetone, Meth; methanol, +; activity, ++ ; ni; no activity, Rf value is the movement of the compound relative to the solvent front.

The information obtained from the chemical spot tests and preliminary chemical analysis of the polypore suggests that the extracts contained phenolic compounds. The polypore, which contained compounds that produced blue to violet spots on TLC plates sprayed with anisaldehyde –sulphuric acid, could be terpenes and phenolics (Stahl and Kaltenbach, 1961; Dawson *et al.*, 1986). Terpenes and phenolics have been implicated in the antibacterial activity of many basidiomycetes fungi (Zjawiony, 2004). The antibacterial activity of these polypores could also be associated with these substances.

Bacillus subtilis produces extracellular enzymes such as polygalacturonase and cellulase that are known for their ability to produce soft rot in plant tissues. *B. subtilis* had been associated with soft rot in potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) (Gordon, 1973; Priest *et al.*, 1988; and Saris *et al.*, 1990). *Pseudomonas syringae* pv *syringae* is associated with bean bacterial brown spot of *syringae vulgaris*. The activity of the two solvent extracts of the polypore show that they could be used for the biocontrol of bacterial brown spot and other bacterial disease incited by *P. syringae* and potato soft rot. The results also provide useful information for authentication of the polypore.

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Corresponding author

Ofodile L. N.

Department of Biological Sciences, Yaba College of Technology, Yaba, Lagos, Nigeria

E-mail: nwannemaka@yahoo.com.